

RRI2SCALE – Regional Report (M1)

REGIONAL REPORT

The purpose of this report is to capture and regularly monitor the integration of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) practices into the Research and Innovation (R&I) governance frameworks and policies of regional authorities. It must be completed by the person representing each regional authority to the RRI2SCALE consortium every four months, beginning from February 2022. The collected answers will improve our understanding of the regional context and, thus, improve the RRI2SCALE approach and activities.

Before proceeding to the questions, reading the following glossary may be helpful to you. For any further clarifications, please don't hesitate to contact Task 5.2 leader (Q-PLAN) at mangelidou@qplan-intl.gr.

- **Research and innovation (R&I)** can be defined as the process of producing new knowledge and the conception and application of better solutions that meet new requirements, unarticulated needs, or existing market needs and lead a region to gain a competitive advantage.
- **R&I ecosystem** is the term used to describe the large number and diverse nature of participants and resources necessary for R&I. These include entrepreneurs, investors, researchers, university faculties, venture capitalists, business development, and other technical service providers.
- **Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)** is a term used to describe scientific research and technological development processes that consider effects and potential impacts on the environment and society. RRI implies that societal actors (researchers, citizens, policy-makers, businesses, etc.) work together during the whole R&I process to align better the R&I activities and outcomes with society's values, needs, and expectations.
- **R&I policy-making process**, in the context of this questionnaire, is defined as any process (e.g., workshop, discussion, committee, consultation and online deliberation) held to decide upon and design policies affecting the research and innovation activities taking place within a region. Indicative examples of R&I policy-making processes are: (i) the entrepreneurial discovery process organised to design the Smart Specialisation Strategy of a region; (ii) a formal discussion between policy-makers on the region's strategic plans; and (iii) a consultation on adopting new technologies, such as a platform, that help the regional authority easier communicate with citizens.

What is your name? *It is highly recommended that always the same person files the report to facilitate comparisons between different periods.*

Q.4.1: Apart from the RRI2SCALE activities, when was it the last time your organisation carried out an R&I policy-making process with some sort of public engagement? *If no such process has taken place since <month that the last regional report was filled in>, please just write "No such process carried out recently".*

If no such process has taken place since <month that the last regional report was filled in>, please ignore the following five questions (Q.4.2-Q.4.6). Otherwise, please reply to them.

Q.4.2: In the above process, what model of public engagement was selected (Public communication/ Public activism/ Public consultation/ Public deliberation/ Public participation)*?

Q.4.3: In the above process, how many people participated and how were they selected? Also, how did you ensure the diversity of the stakeholder group?

Q.4.4: Why do you think these people were eager/incentivised to participate in the above process? Do you generally have strategies and formalised mechanisms in your organisation to engage stakeholders? For example, does your region have a public relations office or a digital marketing manager?

Q.4.5: Which main challenges does your organisation face when engaging the public in an R&I policy-making process?

Q.4.6: Did you employ any measures to encourage interactiveness among participants, collaborative decision-making, and shared responsibility in the above process? If yes, then could you briefly describe them? *For example, did you somehow ensure a gender-equal environment, and did you provide participants with sufficient background knowledge on the topics discussed?*

* (i) Public communication – the aim is to inform and/or educate citizens; (ii) Public activism – the aim is to inform decision-makers and create awareness to influence decision-making processes; (iii) Public consultation – the aim is to inform decision-makers about public opinions on certain topics; (iv) Public deliberation – the aim is to facilitate group deliberation on policy issues, where the outcome may impact decision-making; and (v) Public participation – the aim is to assign partly or full decision-making power to citizens on policy issues.

Q.4.7: What is your role within your organisation? For example, do you exclusively work on research projects such as the RRI2SCALE project, or do you also participate in a decision-making body? Are you a political person or a civil servant? Would you please describe your current job position?

#	Identifier	Question	Very much	Some what	Undecided	Not really	Not at all
1	SP. SC.2	Are the higher-level policy-makers of your region aware of the RRI concept?					
2	SP. SC.3	Do higher-level policy-makers consider the RRI concept as crucial for the R&I ecosystem and the prosperity of your region? (if applicable)					
3	SP. SC.4	Have any of the tools and methods introduced by the RRI2SCALE project, such as the training on stakeholder dialogues, the SES game, the agendas and roadmaps, been communicated by you to higher-level policy-makers to consider their permanent or extended use?					
4	SP. SC.5	Do higher-level policy-makers consider the tools and methods introduced by the RRI2SCALE project as meaningful and plan to use them in the future? (if applicable)					

Q.4.8: Does your organisation currently promotes open access to knowledge and data (e.g., platforms that make available data generated by the regional and local IoT devices)? If yes, then how? *If nothing has changed since <month that the last regional report was filled in>, please just write "nothing changed".*

Q.4.9: Does your organisation take any actions to improve science literacy in the region (e.g., initiatives that educate citizens of all ages about science or generate awareness of science-related issues and a positive image of science)? If yes, then what exactly? *If nothing has changed since <month that the last regional report was filled in>, please just write "nothing changed".*

Q.4.10: Does your organisation take any actions and implement any standards or policies to minimise gender inequality within its governance framework (e.g., requirements for equal representation of both genders in decision-

making bodies)? If yes, then what is it? *If nothing has changed since <month that the last regional report was filled in>, please just write "nothing changed".*

Q.4.11: Does your organisation have in place any mechanism to safeguard ethical standards (e.g., a research ethics committee or a research integrity office). If yes, then what is it? *If nothing has changed since <month that the last regional report was filled in>, please just write "nothing changed".*

Q.4.12: Does your organisation set in place any process to monitor and evaluate the societal, democratic, economic and scientific impact of its policies? If yes, then what is it? *If nothing has changed since <month that the last regional report was filled in>, please just write "nothing changed".*

Q.4.13: Apart from the above, did your organisation recently undertake any other initiatives (e.g., institutional changes) to embed RRI practices into its governance framework? If yes, then could you please describe them? *Examples of such initiatives could be (i) the adoption of new forms of decision-making; (ii) employing methodologies for the engagement of the quadrable helix stakeholders, (iii) a more meaningful public engagement into R&I policy-making processes, and (iv) measures to ensure shared responsibility and ownership of the introduced policies. If nothing has changed since <month that the last regional report was filled in>, please just write "nothing changed".*

Q.4.14: If you positively replied to the above question, then please reply also to this one. Otherwise, please ignore it. Did the RRI2SCALE project contribute in any way to the above initiatives/institutional changes?

Q.4.15: What barriers to embodying RRI practices to your organisation's governance framework have you identified? *If nothing has changed since <month that the last regional report was filled in>, please just write "nothing changed".*

Q.4.16: Would you like to make any suggestions on how RRI2SCALE could improve its current approach, especially when it comes to (i) embodying RRI practices to your organisation's governance framework; and (ii) addressing the Regional Dilemmas of your region? *If nothing has changed since <month that the last regional report was filled in>, please just write "nothing changed".*

Q.4.17: Did any of the stakeholders who participated in the RRI2SCALE activities and workshops inform you that he/she has undertaken any initiative to embed RRI practices into the governance framework of his/her organisation? *If nothing has changed since <month that the last regional report was filled in>, please just write "nothing changed".*

Q.4.18: What issues did you encounter when collecting the above data (e.g., Information silos)?

The regional reports for June and October 2022 also included the following two questions.

Q.4.19: Do you think that the tools and methods introduced by the RRI2SCALE project (such as the training on stakeholder dialogues, the SES, the agendas and roadmaps) would be useful and feasible to be used by your region in the future? If yes, could you provide a few examples? For example, could the SES be used in the preparatory stages of an entrepreneurial discovery process to identify key policy intervention areas? *If nothing has changed since <month that the last regional report was filled in>, please just write "nothing changed".*

Q.4.20: Can you recall in your memory any decision taken (or policy adopted) by the local or regional authority that turned out to not be very successful? Would the situation be different if the public had participated in the decision-making process? For example, electrifying the bus fleet faced great opposition because it overlooked the fact that electric buses can not travel far enough to service remote villages. *If nothing has changed since <month that the last regional report was filled in>, please just write "nothing changed".*